

An Assessment on Business Strategy of Tastes from the Greens Guimba, Nueva Ecija Branch

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Abstract:- This study will determine the marketing strategies of Taste from the Greens for luring and keeping customers. The goal of this paper is to determine the goods offered and the marketing strategies used by the Tastes from the Greens Guimba branch. Scheduled interview and survey questionnaires were used to collect data from employees and customers of Tastes from the Greens Guimba branch. Descriptive method is used which focuses on the business strategy in relation to success and quality management at Tastes from the Greens Guimba. The study shows the age bracket of consumers of the milk tea products and also reveals that there were no significant differences when it comes to socio-economic profile in terms of age, civil status, and monthly income, and in the social factors that impact consumer's purchasing behavior towards milk tea products. Study also reveals the most consumed products of Tastes from the Greens and SWOT analysis of the business. Business strategies of Tastes from the Greens appeals to consumers.

Keywords: Assessment, Marketing Strategy, Milktea business, Tastes

I. INTRODUCTION

The most popular beverage right now is milk tea, one of the trends. There's no doubt that a lot of consumers are attracted to milk tea since in addition to its health advantages, it also has a distinctive flavor and blend. It consists of milk and tea combined with additional flavors and additives. Customers can select from a variety of options. Customers of the new generation fell in love with this product due to its new trend. As a result, business owners see this as a big chance to increase revenue and create a fresh, distinctive product from the originals. Similar to coffee shops, milk tea shops are excellent places for people to hang out, socialize, and pass their leisure time.

Filipinos typically enjoy sipping on cool beverages like "samalamig" and coconut juice, which are perennial favorites. But a new product only recently came into the picture. From the North to the South, milk tea managed to snag the taste buds of every Filipino. Everywhere you walk, you'll find shops and cafes selling milk teas in a variety of tastes.

Filipinos were ranked to be the second highest drinker of milk tea in Southeast Asia. According to Grab Food, (2019) data which caters to thousands of milk tea brands throughout Southeast Asia, an individual in the Philippines consumes an average of five cups of milk tea per month. Compared to Thailand who consumes the highest average of six cups per month individually while other countries like Malaysia, Singapore, Vietnam and Indonesia consume an average of three cups of milk tea per month (Ichimura, 2019).

This popular milk tea shop is proudly homegrown and was founded in The Culinary Capital of the Philippines, Pampanga, where it first opened its doors along McArthur Highway. One of the most well-known milk tea brands in the entire nation, Tastes from the Greens or TFTG acquired a lot of Kapampangan fans before eventually expanding to Metro Manila and other provinces around Luzon. Many enjoyable and intriguing milk tea tastes are available at Tastes from the Greens, which will have you coming back for more. Additionally, the reasonably priced drinks are a surefire customer draw because they give every Filipino the opportunity to experience the chance to sip a cup of creamy and delicious bliss. Prior to the COVID-19 pandemic's arrival in 2020, Tastes from the Greens has already set up 20 branches across the nation. And today, over two years later, Tastes from the Greens is still one of the top milk tea franchisees in the nation, despite the health concern.

This study will determine the marketing strategies of Taste from the Greens for luring and keeping customers. The goal of this paper is to determine the goods offered and the marketing strategies used by the city's chosen milk tea shop. The researchers will carry out this study because it has been noticed that a sizable number of customers go to Taste from the Greens on a regular basis. The quantity of clients is influenced by a variety of things. It can be the several factors that influence consumers when picking a milk tea shop. The marketing strategies implemented by Tastes from the Greens will be the area on which the researchers will concentrate their attention.

II. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The goal of this study is to identify the various marketing techniques used by Taste from the Greens to be able to establish a successful branch in Guimba, Nueva Ecija. This research specifically aims to address the following sub-questions:

- Describe the profile of customers of the shop in terms of:
 - social demographic
 - preferred flavor of milk tea
 - preferred add-on for milk tea
 - duration of visit
 - frequency of visit;
- Determine the average sale, number of cups sold daily, and estimated number of customers in the milk tea shop daily;
- Determine the strength of the business;
- Determine the weakness of the business;
- Determine the opportunity of the business;
- Determine the weakness of the business; and
- Determine the marketing strategies used by Tastes from the Greens that attract the customers.

III. RESEARCH METHOD

The study uses a descriptive method which focuses on the business strategy in relation to success and quality management at Tastes from the Greens Guimba Branch. In addition, an interview schedule is designed as one of the data collection instruments for the study. Also, to obtain a valid and reliable list of data, the primary data were gathered from the employees and customers of Tastes from the Greens Guimba branch using survey questionnaires.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

➤ *Profile of customers*

Table 1. Socio-demographic of Respondents

	Frequency (n=30)	Percentage
Sex		
Female	22	73.33%
Male	8	26.67%
Total	30	100%
Age	Frequency (n=30)	Percentage
17 years old and below	14	46.67%
18 - 26 years old	11	36.67%
27 - 36 years old	3	10%
37 - 46 years old	1	3.33%
47 years old and above	1	3.33%
Total	30	100%
Civil Status	Frequency (n=30)	Percentage
Single	19	63.33%
Married	9	30%
Separated	2	6.67%
Widow	0	0%
Total	30	100%

Table 1 shows the results of the socio-demographic profile of the respondents in terms of sex, age and civil status.

The majority of customers are female with a total number of twenty-two (22) correspondents or 73.33% of the sample, and male customers with a total number of eight (8) correspondents or 26.67% of the sample.

In terms of age, the majority of the respondents are 17 years old and below with a total number of fourteen (14) or 46.67%. Second is the 18-26 years old with a total of eleven (11) or 36.67%. Third is the 27-36 years old with a total number of three (3) or 10%. Fourth is the 37-46 years old with a total of one (1) or 3.33% and fifth is the 47 years old and above is one (1) or 3.33%.

In terms of Civil Status, the majority of the respondents are Single with a total number of nineteen (19) or 63.33%. Married respondents are nine (9) or 30%. Separated respondents are two (2) or 6.67% and Widow respondents are zero (0) or 0%.

Table 2. Preferred flavor of Milk tea of Customers

	Frequency (n=30)	Percentage
Choco Malt Cream Puff	13	43.33%
Cookies & Cream Puff	5	16.67%
Mutcho Matcha Cream Puff	7	23.33%
Winter Melon	2	6.67%
Others	3	10%
Total	30	100%

Table 2 shows the percentage of which Milk tea flavor is usually ordered. The result shows that 43.33% Tastes from the Greens Guimba customers orders Choco Malt Cream Puff which indicates that it is the branch’s best-selling milk tea flavor, while 23.33% of sales is from Mutcho Matcha Cream Puff, 16.67% of daily sales is from Cookies & Cream Puff, 6.67% is from Wintermelon Milk tea, and 10% consist of other milk tea flavors and beverages.

Table 3. Preferred add-on for Milk tea of Customers

	Frequency (n=30)	Percentage
Nata	5	16.67%
Pearls	5	16.67%
Coffee Jelly	4	13.33%
Cream Puff	15	50%
Salted Cream Cheese	1	3.33%
Total	30	100%

Table 3 shows the percentage of milk tea add-ons usually ordered in which reflected in the results that majority of the customers prefer Cream Puff as an add-on on their milk tea with 50%, while both Nata and Pearls have the same percentage of 16.67%, 13.33% of the customers prefer Coffee Jelly while the remaining 3.33% prefers Salted Cream Cheese.

Table 4. Duration per visit of Customers

	Frequency (n=30)	Percentage
Under 1 hour	21	70%
1 - 2 hours	9	30%
3 hours and beyond	0	0%
Total	30	100%

Table 4 shows the result of Duration per visit of Customers. The majority of the respondents with a total of twenty-one (21) or 70% visit the Tastes from the Greens under 1 hour. Nine respondents (9) or 30% visit the milktea shop for 1- 2 hours and zero (0) or 0% for 3 hours and beyond.

Table 5. Frequency of visit of Customers

	Frequency (n=30)	Percentage
1-3 times	25	83.33%
4-6 times	5	16.67%
More than 6 times	0	0%
Total	30	100%

Table 5 shows the frequency of visits of customers at the milk tea shop per month. Majority of the correspondents (83.33% of the sample size) visits Tastes from the Greens only for 1-3 times a month, while 16.67% of the respondents visit for about 4-6 times monthly, and there is 0% of respondents that visits the shop more than 6 times in a month.

➤ *Average sale, number of cups sold daily, and estimated number of customers in the milk tea shop daily*

To keep a business going, it is important to monitor sales daily. Since sales are the lifeblood of any company, it is important to know what is in the sales funnel at all times and how much revenue to expect from current opportunities. Tastes from the Greens Guimba branch sold an average of 70 cups per day with average sales ranging from ₱9,000.00 - ₱10,000.00 daily.

Customers are the central factor in every company. Customers buy products and services and give feedback to businesses on how to improve their services better. Without customers, no company can survive. Customers also play an important role in promoting one’s business, may it be to recommend to others or warn them against availing the products or services. Tastes from the Greens Guimba branch have an average of 30 walk-in customers daily.

➤ *SWOT Analysis of Tastes from the Greens Guimba, Nueva Ecija Branch*

Table 6 SWOT Analysis of Tastes from the Greens Guimba, Nueva Ecija Branch

STRENGTHS	WEAKNESSES
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● affordability of the product offered ● one of the pioneers in the local milk tea industry ● Unique milk tea flavors ● Positive attitudes to the brand <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Good location 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● unexpected volume of the customers ● High cost yet small location ● No company application ● No online payment options ● Many substitutes competitive products ● Operates a single store model
OPPORTUNITIES	THREATS

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● venture into the online marketing platforms ● large potential market ● maximize product scope ● Introduce or broaden food menu ● Introduce an app or QR menu for ordering 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● local competitors offering wide variety of milk tea flavors ● advanced marketing strategy of competitors in this industry ● Seasonal demand: winter and summer are different ● Increase in supplier costs – rental and staff costs
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➤ *Marketing strategies used by Tastes from the Greens that attract the customers*

Different companies practice different marketing strategies. Aside from relying on word-of-mouth from customers, Tastes from the Greens advertises their business by printing posters and tarpaulins, and distribution of flyers. Tastes from the Greens Guimba also offers delivery, curbside and pick-up. If within 3 km reach, with a minimum of three (3) orders, they will deliver it for free. At the milk tea shop, different board and mind games are prepared for customers to enjoy and avoid getting bored while orders are being prepared; the board and mind games also add extra fun for families, friends, and even for an individual when dining at the milk tea shop. There is also a monthly raffle for the loyal customers of Tastes from the Greens Guimba.

Since Tastes from the Greens is a family owned and homegrown business, all members of the family have undergone series and numerous training and seminars regarding Milk teas, and different kinds of beverages. Tastes from the Greens heads also make sure to conduct a monthly visit in every branch in order to monitor and check how the business is doing. Tastes from the Greens continuous development and innovation of products is also one of their vital marketing strategies.

IV.CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The purpose of this study is to assess and evaluate the business strategy of Tastes from the Greens Guimba. The study conducted shows that the consumers of the milk tea products are mostly teenagers who are 22 and below, single with a high school or college degree. The study also reveals that there were no significant differences when it comes to socio-economic profile in terms of age, civil status, and monthly income, and in the social factors that impact consumer’s purchasing behavior towards milk tea products.

The study shows that Tastes from the Greens milk tea flavor best seller is Choco Malt Cream Puff and Cream Puff as milk tea add on. It's always a good sign when a particular product becomes a best-seller, as it shows that customers appreciate the taste and quality of the item. It's important for businesses to keep innovating and offering new and exciting flavors and products to keep their customers coming back for more.

Taste from the Greens is conveniently located for the majority of their customers, as 70% of the respondents reported visiting the establishment in under an hour. This is a good indication that the business is easily accessible and convenient for its target audience. Every business should consider the location and accessibility of their establishment when planning their business strategy, as this can have a significant impact on customer traffic and sales. By being located in a convenient location, Taste from the Greens is likely to attract more customers and generate more revenue.

The majority of respondents (83.33% of the sample size) visit Tastes from the Greens only 1-3 times per month. This could be due to a number of factors, such as customers living or working in the area, space of the store location and visiting the establishment when it's convenient for them, or customers who enjoy the products but may not have the opportunity to visit frequently due to other commitments or preferences.

Through SWOT analysis, it is revealed that the strength of the Tastes from the Greens Guimba aside from being one of the pioneers in the local milk tea industry, is the unique taste and flavors offered by the business. Their weakness is despite the good store location, it appears to be small and the unavailability of any online payment option. Tastes from the Greens gave an opportunity with a large potential market but advanced marketing strategy of competitors in this industry can be seen as a threat to their business.

Taste from the Greens should consider innovating their products that will help to improve their success as a company. This can be giving the product a new flavor or presenting items that go well with their drinks, including pizza, burgers, fries, and chicken, exactly like their rival milk tea shops.

Tastes from the Greens should also consider investing in an advertising tool like Facebook promotions and websites that might also draw in a new target market if they want to increase the size of their target market. Since almost everything is being done online, a cashless transaction should also be considered by the business. Given that their items may cost more than those of their competitors, they should think about rewarding and discounting their customers.

Tastes from the Greens should consider understanding their customers' behavior and preferences when it comes to frequency of visits, as this can help them tailor their business strategy and marketing efforts. For example, if the majority of customers only visit 1-3 times per month, Taste from the Greens may want to focus on increasing the average transaction value per visit to maximize revenue from each customer. Alternatively, they may want to consider introducing loyalty programs or other incentives to encourage customers to visit more frequently. It may also be thought of as having a good, comfortable space because it draws more customers. A trend that would also be used is to design the shop based on each season.

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